

THE PASTORAL COUNSELLORS

JOURNAL *of* **NIGERIAN ASSOCIATION OF PASTORAL COUNSELLORS**

In collaboration with
Department of Religious and Intercultural Studies
and
Department of Guidance and Counselling
LEAD CITY UNIVERSITY, IBADAN, NIGERIA

VOL. 3. MAY 2024

ISSN: PRINT 2971-5199 ONLINE 2971-5202

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Redemptive Excommunication in Matthew 18:15-20 and Its Implications for Pastoral Counselling in the Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria

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Abstract

Redemptive excommunication is a component of church discipline through which the church corrects sinful behaviour in the congregation or removes a sinful person from the membership. Through the centuries the church has shown vital concern about how to discipline and restore its erring members. Jesus in Mathew 18:15-20 instructed the church to treat an erring member who refuses correction as they would a pagan or a tax collector. Keeping heretic and immoral members within the fold posed serious danger to its existence. This researcher is goaded by this scenario to write this paper. Past and recent works on settling church dispute is replete but none has brought in the expulsion of unrepentant erring member as measure of preservation of the remaining faithful members of the church. The methodology adopted is historical and exegetical. The study discovered that Church discipline is neither the exclusive responsibility nor the prerogative of church leaders. Also, discipline does not first push the contamination out of the church but rather draws the erring back to church. The researcher recommends that the first task of the church leaders is to develop churches in which people really know and care for one another. The first disciplinary approach should be made in private. That a member is excommunicated does not mean that the church should abandon him. Excommunication should be redemptive both to the erring and the members of the church. The full restoration of excommunicated member should be an expression of pastoral care in its motive and effect.

Keywords: Counselling, Discipline, Excommunication, Pastoral, Redemptive

Introduction

Within the realm of Christian ministry and pastoral care, one of the most challenging and theologically significant matters that confront the Church is the issue of discipline and restoration within the body of believers. The Gospel of Matthew, in particular, provides us with a profound and redemptive framework for addressing this sensitive topic. In Matthew 18:15-20, we find the words of Jesus, our Lord, and Savior, who presents a divine blueprint for reconciling and restoring those who have strayed from the fold. This passage is not merely a set of instructions; it is a sacred mandate, a scriptural revelation of divine wisdom aimed at preserving the sanctity of the Christian community while exemplifying the mercy and grace of the Triune God.

The heart of this research lies in "redemptive excommunication," a term that may appear paradoxical at first glance. Yet, in exploring the depths of Matthew 18:15-20, we discover a divine paradox—the simultaneous need for discipline and grace, correction and compassion. In its

essence, redemptive excommunication signifies the act of removing an unrepentant believer from the fellowship of the Church for the purpose of reconciliation and restoration. It is a process bathed in love, designed to draw the erring one back to the path of righteousness, safeguarding not only the purity of the Church but also the soul of the wandering sheep. The burden of this is that despite the fact works has been done on the subject of excommunication in the church, none has addressed the removal of erring member as a measure of preservation of the remaining faithful members who may be prone to contamination from the unrepentant erring member if not removed. This study delves into the profound theological implications of redemptive excommunication as outlined in Matthew 18:15-20, seeking to unearth the treasures of divine wisdom that guide the Church in its role as a community of grace, love, and transformation. Furthermore, this research aims to examine how this divine directive interfaces with the realm of pastoral counseling, a sacred discipline within Christian ministry among the Pentecostal churches in Nigeria.

I. Definition of Terms

A. Redemptive Excommunication

Excommunication is the disciplinary action of a local church to remove one of its members from the membership on the basis of his or her stubborn disobedience to the commands of Christ, or divisive distortions of the doctrines of Christ. It is the end of the disciplinary process. It declares that although the person may profess Christ with his or her mouth, they have denied him by their way of life. Excommunication, therefore, puts to an end all of the benefits of Christian fellowship for the one excommunicated. It also puts and end the obligations of the Church as it pertains to the care of the persons soul (Anady, 2012). Excommunication is the word that we use to describe what Christ stated in Matthew 18:17, saying, "If he refuses to listen to them, tell it to the church. And if he refuses to listen even to the church, let him be to you as a Gentile and a tax collector" (Matthew 18:17, ESV). To excommunicate is to put a person out of the church and into the world, for his or her unrepentant way of life has made it plain that that is where he or she belongs – in the world and not in the church, according to Anady (2012).

The term redemptive Excommunication is a term used in certain Christian contexts to describe a process by which an individual who is a member of a church community, and who is in unrepentant sin, is temporarily or permanently removed from the fellowship of the church. The primary purpose of redemptive excommunication is to bring about repentance and restoration in the individual's life.

B. Pastoral Counselling

Counselling could be said to refer to a number of procedures used in assisting an individual in solving problems which arise in various aspects of his life or in assisting him to maximize his overall personal development so that he could be more effective, satisfied and more useful to the society in which he lives. The nature of counselling, according to Patterson, is to be found in the following characteristics:

1. Counselling is concerned with influencing voluntary behavioural change on the part of the client or counselee.

2. The purpose of counselling is to provide condition that facilitates voluntary in behaviour.
3. As in all relationship, limits are imposed on the counselee by counselling goals that are influenced by the counsellor's values and philosophy.
4. Conditions facilitating behavioural change are provided through interview (not all counselling is interviewing, but interview is always involved).
5. Listening is present in counselling but not all counselling is listening.
6. The counsellor understands clients.
7. Counselling is conducted in privacy and the discussion is confidential (Abidogun, 2022).

According to Abidogun (2022), Pastoral counselling is also known as ministerial or religious counselling. In Banner's (1992, pp. 56-57) opinion, pastoral counselling involves the establishment of a time-limited relationship that is structured to provide comfort for troubled persons by enhancing their awareness of God's grace and faithful presence and thereby increasing their ability to live their lives more fully in the light of these realizations.

C. The Nexus

Pastoral counselling and redemptive excommunication can complement each other. Pastoral counselling is often the first step in addressing issues of sin or spiritual waywardness. If counselling does not lead to repentance and restoration, the church may proceed with redemptive excommunication. These approaches can be sequential. A person who initially receives pastoral counselling may face excommunication if they continue in unrepentant sin. Redemptive excommunication is a more severe step and is typically considered after other attempts at reconciliation have been exhausted. The key to the relationship between pastoral counselling and redemptive excommunication is that both are motivated by love, grace, and a desire for the individual's spiritual well-being. The hope is that through counselling and, if necessary, excommunication, the person may ultimately come to a place of repentance and restoration (Tomlinson, 2020).

II. Goal of Redemptive Excommunication

Redemptive excommunication also refers to "corrective church discipline", with a primary purpose of discipling, has five goals; reconciliation, purity, restoration, freedom and communal value. Below, each goal will be articulated theologically to provide a more precise understanding of the construct of corrective church discipline:

Reconciliation: The primary objective is to achieve reconciliation, which can be defined as the transformation of hostility into friendship. This concept of reconciliation is deeply rooted in the nature of the Trinity, which is characterized by love. The Triune God, being loving, eternally exists in a state of perfect community (Grenz, 1998, p. 47). The church is called to partner with Christ in this ministry of reconciliation, one aspect of which includes corrective church discipline. Spirit-filled love conditions the attitudes and actions in which the reconciliation processes are to be exercised. These attitudes include gentleness, humility, sorrow, forgiveness, and brotherliness. The posture of reconciling corrective discipline is sorrow for a brother or sister who is trapped, and not condemnation for an enemy who is to be injured (Hull, 1993, p. 147).

Purity: The second goal of the corrective discipling process is purity. Purity is anchored in the holy character of God. The church is called to the moral responsibility of purity on the basis of God's holiness. One aspect of this participation is through corrective discipline in which the believer caught in sin is called back to the life of personal purity (Grenz, 1998, p. 49).

Restoration: The third goal of corrective church discipling is restoration. Restoration, through discipline, is the gracious action of God. Restorative action issues from God's character of love and more precisely His particular love for the church. God's restorative discipline is neither punishment nor judgement. The church is called to partner with God in the ministry of restoration. In fact, restoration within the church is the ministry of Christ working by the Holy Spirit through the church in perfecting the church. The believer who is "caught" (*prolambano*) in sin is "trapped," "bound by," or "in bondage to" to sin. Those that are spiritual are commanded to restore that individual. The idea of restoring is renewing someone to usefulness. The verb - restore (*katarizo*) in Galatians 6:1 is a medical term that was used in secular Greek for setting a fractured bone (Grenz, 1998, p. 49).

Freedom: The fourth goal of corrective discipline is freedom. Sin always causes enslavement. Alternatively, living in righteousness brings Christian freedom. This freedom is not the right to do as one pleases as advocated by the individualism of Western culture. Rather, freedom is the power and capacity both to will and to do as one ought. The freedom of Christian liberty is freedom from sin in order to be like Jesus Christ. Christian liberty is never freedom from responsibility. Rather, it is responsibility for choice and empowerment for right choice. Thus, through restoration of members who have been caught in sin there is a new liberty that is realized within the church (Sider, 2005, 45).

Communal Value: In addition to the aforementioned, the writer believes that another goal of corrective discipline is establishment of communal values where the place and the roles of the elders within the community are highly celebrated and the community is seen as more important collectively than an individual. Adamo listed that a sense of the community, a sense of good human relations, a sense of sacredness of life, a sense of hospitality, a sense of sacredness of everything and religion, and a sense of respect for authority and elders who are in possession of wisdom by virtue of their experience should be celebrated. (Adamo, 2015, p. 11).

III. An Exegetical Study of Matthew 18:15-20

A. Background of Study

The anonymity of the four Gospel writers is a serious issue in scholarship since the Gospels are unlike the epistles which follow certain writing styles that easily identify the writers. According to France (1989, pp. 50-1), there are scholars who argue that the names of the authors of the Gospel books were a later addition by the Church about 215 CE. The authorship of Matthew received the most criticism because it was not only nameless but both the internal and external evidences seem to go against the traditional view of Matthean authorship. Hence, so many notable scholars have decided to disagree with the traditional authorship of Matthew, one of the 12 apostles. In response to Green's arguments, the following ensues: (a) —The structure and composition of the Gospel show that the evangelist is influenced by Jewish literature. Green (2000, pp. 19-27) argues that the Gospel of Matthew has almost no link to Hebrew and/or Aramaic even though Papias

had reported it was written in Hebrew instead of Greek which he said is misleading. Kurzinger suggests Papias's statement means: Matthew arranged the traditions in a Jewish manner (Luz, 2001, 46). Therefore, this implies that Matthew used and arranged other materials like Mark, Q (and other early Christian traditions) in the above manner. This may also explain the existing literary relationship of Gospel books and their different arrangements. (b) Probably —[t]he Matthean sources, Mark and Q, [may] have been arrayed and circulated in Jewish Christian community before the writing of Matthew. (c) The author's familiarity with Jewish concepts and environment, the Law and the Old Testament suggests a Jewish author.

Hengel refutes claims that titles were later added to the first century gospels by the Church and presented a thought-provoking thesis contrary to that assumption. He based his research on—the nature of references to the gospels in the second-century Christian literature, and the general practice of book-distribution in the Greek world, where titles were necessary for identification of a work to which reference might be made. Therefore, Hengel's argument is that it would be very unlikely to have such sacred documents in circulation among the Christian communities in the late first century without proper reference to their authorship (France, 1989, p. 50).

Therefore, it is reasonable to argue with the Church tradition on the authorship of Matthew as one of the twelve apostles of Jesus. Moreover, Keener (1999, p. 41) rightly observes that: —some scholars who reject Matthean authorship are troubled by the antiquity of the Gospel titles and the tradition of authorship ... [even though] too many scholars simply ignore these difficulties. The place of writing has been argued mostly for Egypt, Palestine and Syria among Bible scholars. For example: Brandon singled out Alexandria as the place of writing due to the significant presence of a good number of Jews in the city; for they were the next leading practicing Jewish community after the destruction of the Temple and the disorganization of the Jewish community in Jerusalem (France, 1989, p. 51). France (1989, p. 51) appears more inclined to the Palestinian origin of the gospel. The option of Syria is divided between either Antioch or Tyre (or one of the neighbouring Phoenician cities) The preceding discussion suggests that the author's place of writing may also be the same locality of his immediate recipients. The date of writing may be (a) either before or after AD 70; (b) the early second century.

B. Textual Consideration of Matthew 18:15-20

15 "Ἐὰν δὲ ἀμάρτη εἰς σὲ ὁ ἀδελφός σου, ὑπάγε ἐλεγξον αὐτὸν μεταξὺ σοῦ καὶ αὐτοῦ μόνου. ἐὰν σοῦ ἀκούσῃ, ἐκέρδησας τὸν ἀδελφόν σου.

16 ἐὰν δὲ μὴ ἀκούσῃ, παράλαβε μετὰ σοῦ ἓτι ἓνα ἢ δύο, ἵνα ἐπὶ στόματος δύο μαρτύρων ἢ τριῶν σταθῇ πᾶν ῥῆμα.

17 ἐὰν δὲ παρακούσῃ αὐτῶν, εἰπὲ τῇ ἐκκλησίᾳ. ἐὰν δὲ καὶ τῆς ἐκκλησίας παρακούσῃ, ἔστω σοι ὡσπερ ὁ ἐθνικός καὶ ὁ τελώνης.

18 Ἀμὴν λέγω ὑμῖν, ὅσα ἐὰν δήσητε ἐπὶ τῆς γῆς, ἔσται δεδεμένα ἐν οὐρανῷ, καὶ ὅσα ἐὰν λύσητε ἐπὶ τῆς γῆς, ἔσται λελυμένα ἐν οὐρανῷ.

19 Πάλιν [Ἀμὴν] λέγω ὑμῖν ὅτι ἐὰν δύο ἐξ ὑμῶν συμφωνήσωσιν ἐπὶ τῆς γῆς περὶ παντὸς πράγματος οὗ ἐὰν αἰτήσωνται, γενήσεται αὐτοῖς παρὰ τοῦ πατρὸς μου τοῦ ἐν οὐρανοῖς.

20 Ὅπου γάρ εἰσιν δύο ἢ τρεῖς συνηγμένοι εἰς τὸ ἕμὸν ὄνομα, ἐκεῖ εἰμι ἐν μέσῳ αὐτῶν."

NIV English Version

"If your brother or sister sins, go and point out their fault, just between the two of you. If they listen to you, you have won them over.

But if they will not listen, take one or two others along, so that 'every matter may be established by the testimony of two or three witnesses.'

If they still refuse to listen, tell it to the church; and if they refuse to listen even to the church, treat them as you would a pagan or a tax collector.

Truly I tell you, whatever you bind on earth will be bound in heaven, and whatever you loose on earth will be loosed in heaven.

Again, truly I tell you that if two of you on earth agree about anything they ask for, it will be done for them by my Father in heaven.

For where two or three gather in my name, there am I with them."

C. Structural Flow of Matthew 18:15-20

Title: Restoring Fractured Fellowship: The Redemptive Process of Matthew 18:15-20

- I. Private Confrontation (Matthew 18:15)
- II. Involving Witnesses (Matthew 18:16)
- III. Church Involvement (Matthew 18:17)
- IV. Redemptive Excommunication as a Last Resort
- V. Divine Authority (Matthew 18:18)
- VI. Power of Agreement (Matthew 18:19)
- VII. Christ's Presence (Matthew 18:20)

D. Literary Context of Matthew 18:15-20

In Matthew 18:15-20, we find a passage that addresses the early Christian community's transition from the old covenant to the new covenant. This shift calls for new ethical guidelines and a deeper understanding of faith and how it translates into daily life. The passage centers on the term "ἐκκλησία" (*ekklēsia*), meaning "church," which is mentioned only twice in the Gospels. The first instance occurs in Matthew 16:18, where Jesus declares the foundation of His church upon Peter's confession of His messiahship. This declaration marks the beginning of the new community. The passage also reflects the disciples' struggles in comprehending the sacrificial aspect of Christ's mission, as seen in Peter's rebuke of Jesus and their general misunderstanding. Matthew 18:15-20 deals with conflict resolution and confronting sin within the faith community. It stresses reconciliation, mutual accountability, and the presence of Christ throughout the process. The teachings in this passage connect to earlier discussions on causing others to sin, the parable of the lost sheep, and the concept of perishing, emphasizing the need for mutual correction and care within the community. This passage provides guidance to the new faith community as they navigate their journey in this new covenant (Hare, 1993, p. 2).

E. Textual Analysis of Matthew 18:15-20

The use of the Greek conditional construct "Ἐάν" (if) is notable in this passage, appearing nine times from verses 15 to 20. The use of the Greek conditional construct "Ἐάν" (if) is notable in this passage, appearing nine times from verses 15 to 20. This suggests that the pursuit of acceptable and ethical standards, as instructed by Jesus, may not always yield the desired outcomes. The effectiveness of these standards is contingent upon the choices made by individuals within the faith community (Wallace, 1996, p. 696):

The presence of the ἔάν clause serves as a bridge between verse 19 and the preceding verses 15 to 17. Furthermore, the contrast between actions "on earth" and "in heaven" creates a connection to verse 18. Consequently, verses 19 and 20 maintain a strong connection with the previous verses, forming a distinct unit. It's worth noting that the use of the word "everything" (πάντα) to connect verses 18 and 19 raises questions regarding the logical relationship between these two verses (Wallace, 1996, p. 696).

Verse 18 in the first half addresses a specific conflict situation which if it has not yet happened probably will in the near future; consequently, it conveys steps to respond to it. Verse 19 in the second half addresses a general condition because of the Greek words πεξὶ παληῶ concerning anything. However, it appears that the specific condition mentioned in verse 18 is a subset to the general condition mentioned in verse 19 because of πεξὶ παληῶ. There is a movement from a singular offender to plural which has also affected number in Greek (Luz, 2007, p. 448). The NIV rightly follows the rhythm of the movement while the NRSV does not.

The clause "Ἐάν δὲ ἁμαρτήσῃ ὁ ἀδελφός σου" or "But if your brother sins [against you]" is closely linked to the context of avoiding actions that lead others into sin. When someone within the faith community wrongs another believer, the response of the offended party is crucial. They can either respond in a way that avoids sin or succumb to temptation. While the offender is clearly at fault for causing another to sin, the individual being influenced has the power to choose their response, which ultimately determines whether they, too, commit a sin. This highlights the importance of individual choices when faced with wrongdoing (Gundry, 1994, p. 376). The second mention of the ἐθθεζία appears in v. 17 where there is need for healing a hurting relationship within the faith community. The first mention of ἐθθεζία in chapter 16 calls attention to its foundation and what needs be done for its firmness; while the second mention in chapter 18 calls attention to a part of its missional. The ἐθθεζία in verse 18 has been saddled with the responsibility to δήζεηε θαὶ ἰχζεηε bind and loose which summons the entire community of faith to respond in unity. This may connect between the responsibility in verse 18 and the preceding verses 15–17: people in the community whose faith and ethics are persistently incongruent (vv. 15–17) should be δήζεηε but only if they repent would they be ἰχζεηε.

Matthew somewhat differs with the Lukan account even though they seem to point to the same event. According to Gundry (1994, p. 376), the Lukan account was not concerned about the steps outlined by Matthew or the place of the Church of the faith community in resolving conflict among believers. The Greek terms "ἀδελφο" (brother) and "ἀδελθή" (sister), as indicated in the word study, encompass both physical and spiritual relationships. In a spiritual context, these terms unite all individuals who are justified by their faith in Jesus into one family of God.

However, this spiritual connection also necessitates that Jesus' disciples exhibit godly character. Consequently, the significance of these words goes beyond merely being a disciple who listens to Jesus' teachings. It encompasses both listening and obeying the divine revelation provided by God through Jesus Christ (as seen in passages like Mark 3:31–35, Matthew 25:40, Matthew 28:10, and John 20:17). Failing to live in accordance with this teaching results in a disconnect between our professed beliefs and our actions, highlighting the importance of aligning our confession of faith with our conduct (Hare, 1993, p. 213).

F. Conclusion of the interpretation of Matthew 18:15-20

The message is crystal clear, emphasizing that the integrity of any faith community hinges significantly on how it responds to a brother or sister within its midst who sins and continues in that sin. The handling of such situations is a critical factor. It's essential to look to Scripture for guidance, especially in challenging circumstances where the individual causing offense is unrepentant and holds influence within the faith community, to the extent that they might leave if disciplined. So, how should the community navigate these complex and controversial situations? Matthew provides a response: First, the faith community should recall its foundational principles and the source of its existence. Second, they must remember their responsibilities to all members within the faith community. Third, they should also consider their responsibilities to those outside the faith community. Additionally, Matthew may want the faith community to keep these things in mind:

- a) While engaging in reconciliation and restoration, they should not be disheartened by the fact that there may be exceptions, with certain members persisting in their wrongdoing.
- b) Leaders of the faith community should exercise their privilege responsibly and not misuse it.
- c) The members of the community should be supportive of the decision to excommunicate a member who continues in their wrongdoing.
- d) Lastly, it's important to remember that Jesus Christ has promised to assist the community in their efforts to instill deep faith and ethics within the faith community.

IV. Application of Redemptive Ex-Communication in Matthew 18:15-20 for Pastoral Counselling

Redemptive excommunication, as highlighted in this passage, involves a process of addressing sin within the community with the ultimate goal of restoring the erring member. It emphasizes the need for personal responsibility and mutual care. In the context of pastoral counselling, this passage offers valuable insights:

Conflict Resolution: Pastoral counsellors can draw from the principles of addressing conflicts laid out in this passage. It emphasizes the importance of addressing issues one-on-one and in a spirit of gentleness and love, which can be applied in counselling sessions to encourage constructive communication and reconciliation.

Accountability: The concept of accountability is central in both redemptive excommunication and pastoral counselling. In counselling, individuals can be encouraged to take responsibility for their actions and seek forgiveness or make amends when necessary.

Community Involvement: The involvement of the faith community in the process of addressing sin and facilitating restoration highlights the significance of a supportive and caring community. Pastoral counselling can encourage individuals to seek support from their faith community and involve their spiritual leaders when facing challenges.

Restoration: The ultimate goal of redemptive excommunication is restoration. Similarly, pastoral counselling should focus on the restoration of individuals to a place of spiritual and emotional well-being. Counsellors can use the process outlined in Matthew 18:15-20 as a model for facilitating healing and growth.

Prayer and Guidance: Pastoral counselling often involves prayer and seeking divine guidance. The passage emphasizes the power of agreement in prayer and the presence of Jesus in the midst of the faith community. This can inspire pastoral counsellors to incorporate prayer and spiritual guidance into their sessions.

In conclusion, Matthew 18:15-20 offers valuable insights for pastoral counselling within the context of redemptive excommunication. It underscores the importance of addressing conflicts, accountability, community support, restoration, and spiritual guidance, which are all vital components of effective pastoral counselling.

Conclusion

In summary, the study of redemptive excommunication in Matthew 18:15-20 and its implications for pastoral counselling in the Pentecostal churches in Nigeria, reveals a compassionate and structured approach to addressing conflicts and promoting restoration in the faith community. If the Pentecostal Churches in Nigeria applied the process and procedure for redemptive excommunication, most of the problems of heretical teachings, immoral acts, embezzlement and misappropriation of funds, and the likes would have been curbed and curtailed to a very large extent. This process emphasizes reconciliation, accountability, and ultimately seeks to guide individuals back to a path of righteousness. Lastly, it can be stated that redemptive excommunication, as outlined in Matthew 18:15-20, offers a pathway to resolve conflicts with the ultimate goal of bringing individuals back into the fold, ensuring the well-being and unity of the faith community. This process holds significant implications for pastoral counselling, promoting accountability and healing within the faith community of the Pentecostals.

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